

e-ISSN: 3048-6017

Volume 09 Issue 01
Jan-Apr 2026***Corresponding Author :**

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Submission Date: Feb
22, 2026

Copyright Received

Date: Feb 23, 2026

**Seismic Wave Scattering by the Izmir–
Ankara–Erzincan Suture Zone in the
West of Turkey****Maryam Gashmard^{1*}, Shahrouz Gashmard²**

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ABSTRACT

Seismic wave scattering is commonly observed during wave propagation through heterogeneous media, providing important information about crustal and lithospheric structures. In this study, body-to-surface wave scattering caused by strong lateral heterogeneities in western Turkey is investigated using teleseismic data recorded by 82 broadband seismic stations from temporary and permanent networks. The analysis focuses on the conversion of SH body waves into Love surface waves generated by geological scatterers. The earthquake of 27 July 2014 (Mw 6.4) in the Atlantic Ocean was selected as the seismic source. Phase coherence analysis was applied to broadband recordings to detect weak but coherent scattered signals. The observed scattered Love waves exhibit a dominant period of approximately 10 s and propagate with an apparent velocity of about 3.17 km s^{-1} . Scatterer locations were estimated using a back-projection approach based on a straight-ray approximation. The results indicate that the main scattering sources are concentrated along the Izmir–Ankara–Erzincan Suture Zone. This major tectonic boundary, together with its pronounced structural contrasts and topographic gradients, likely plays an important role in scattering seismic waves. Our results demonstrate that strong lateral variations in seismic velocity or density associated with suture zones and fault systems can act as efficient seismic scatterers.

Keywords: seismic scattering, lateral heterogeneity, SH–Love conversion, back projection, phase coherence, teleseismic waves

INTRODUCTION

Seismic scattering observations indicate that structural heterogeneities are widespread throughout the Earth. Since the 1970s, numerous theoretical and observational studies have attempted to understand the relationship between crustal and lithospheric heterogeneity and seismic wave scattering [6,8]. Early investigations commonly employed stochastic approaches to describe scattering, which allowed only for statistical characterization of the heterogeneities. In earthquake seismology, several imaging techniques rely on wave conversions. For example, receiver function analysis utilizes P-to-S conversions to image discontinuities in the crust and upper mantle [1,5,6,8] Wu, 1985;. However, most traditional methods assume subhorizontal layering and are therefore less effective for imaging strong lateral heterogeneities such as near-vertical structures. In exploration seismology, complex structures can be imaged using dense arrays of sources and receivers together with advanced techniques such as reverse-time migration or full waveform inversion [9]. In contrast, earthquake seismology often suffers from sparse distributions of sources and seismic stations, which limits the ability to resolve subsurface structures such as basin edges, fault zones, suture zones, and Moho offsets (Shearer, 2007). Body-to-surface wave scattering provides an alternative approach to investigating such structures.

The study of scattered seismic waves can help identify strong scatterers and thus improve our understanding of geological structures and deformation processes in the crust and lithosphere. In this context, the conversion of SH body waves to Love waves is particularly useful for detecting lateral heterogeneities within the shallow crust [10,11,12]. This study focuses on the identification of a seismic scatterer located in western Turkey using teleseismic recordings from seismic arrays deployed in northwestern Iran.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY**Seismic Data**

The shallow crustal structure has a significant impact on the velocity of love waves. So, body-to-surface wave scattering is a method to detect shallow crustal heterogeneities. Broadband waveform data from 82 seismic stations were used in this study. These stations belong to several regional and temporary seismic arrays, including the Deylaman, Tarom, and Iran–China networks deployed in northwestern Iran. The configuration of these arrays provides favorable azimuthal coverage for detecting scattered seismic energy generated by teleseismic events (Figure 1). Information about the stations used in this study is given in Table1. A teleseismic earthquake that occurred on 27 July 2014 (Mw 6.4) in the Atlantic Ocean was selected as the primary event because of its clear SH arrivals and high signal-to-noise ratio across the network.

Table 1: Information of different Arrays used in this study.

Num	Name of Array	Number of stations	Type of array	Duration of data collection
1	Deylaman	23	Permanent	2008/08-2012/06
2	Tarom	21	Permanent	2012/06-2014-09
3	Iran-China	63	Permanent	2013/09-2014/10

Fig. 1: Map of the stations in the North West of Iran. Solid triangles mark broadband stations.

Data Processing

The initial processing of seismic waveforms involved several steps. First, the instrument response was removed, and the data were spectrally equalized to account for differences among recording systems. The three-component seismograms were then rotated from the vertical–north–east coordinate system into vertical, radial, and tangential components according to the source–receiver geometry. The data were band-pass filtered between 0.02 and 0.1 Hz using a zero-phase Butterworth filter. Subsequently, the traces were aligned relative to the arrival of the SH phase and normalized by the peak amplitude of this phase. Time windows extending from 50 s before to 400 s after the SH arrival were selected for further analysis. Records with excessive noise or poor phase coherence were removed after visual inspection.

Phase Coherence Analysis

This method was originally described by Schimmel and Paulssen (1997). Phase coherence analysis is superior to conventional linear beamforming techniques in detecting weak but coherent signals. This method relies on the instantaneous phase. Real seismic traces

are first converted to analytic traces by applying a Hilbert transform. The amplitudes of analytic traces are normalized to unity. Phase coherence $c(t)$ is then constructed by a summation of analytic traces in the complex plane [7], that is,

$$C(t) = s(t) + iH(s(t)) = A(t) \exp [i \Phi(t)] \quad (1)$$

where $s(t)$ is the real part of traces and $H(s(t))$ is Hilbert transform. $\Phi_j(t)$ is the instantaneous phase of the j th trace. The amplitude and phase of the vector are written as a time variable t . Since amplitude $A(t)$ is normalized, the value of phase coherence ranges between 0 and 1. The results obtained from the phase analysis, including the travel time diagram and the time-frequency diagram of the earthquake, are shown in Figure 2. In the travel time diagram, the horizontal axis is time in seconds, plotted in the time interval from -50 to 500 seconds relative to the SH phase, and the vertical axis is the distance from the source to each station in kilometers (Figure 2a). The shear waves are seen with relatively high amplitude and very high coherence due to the large magnitude of the earthquake. The

interesting thing about the maps is that the highest amplitude is related to the PS phase. In the time-frequency diagram, the horizontal axis is time in seconds, plotted over a time interval of -50 to 450 seconds relative to the SH phase, and the vertical axis is the slowness in seconds per degree (Figure 2b).

The considered slowness values range from zero to 40 because the slowness values of shear waves and Love waves are not outside this range. Phase coherence

values range from zero to one, determined by the color of each phase. For example, the SH wave and the PS phase have a coherence close to one, indicating a high coherence percentage. The slowness of these phases is in the range of 13 seconds per degree, which is equivalent to a speed of 8.54 km/s. In contrast, scattered waves, which are also numerous, are seen in the slowness range of 33 to 36 seconds per degree, which is equivalent to a speed of 3.08 to 3.36 km/s.

Fig. 2: a) Transverse component seismograms sorted by distance to the earthquake source. b) Slowness time diagram of phase coherence across the scattered waves.

SCATTERER LOCALIZATION

The locations of scattering sources were estimated using a back-projection technique. Accurate scatterer positioning requires knowledge of seismic velocities. While the arrival times of direct SH waves can be predicted reliably using reference Earth models such as IASP91, estimating travel times of scattered Love waves is

$$\Delta x = \frac{(Vb \times Vs)}{Vb - Vs} \times \Delta t \quad (2)$$

Where Δx is the distance between the station and the scatterer, Vb is the velocity

more challenging due to their slower propagation.

The distance between a station and a scatterer along the propagation path was calculated using the differential travel time between the body wave and the scattered surface wave:

of the body wave, Vs is the velocity of the scattered surface wave, and Δt is the

differential time between body and scattered surface waves.

RESULTS

The strength of body-to-surface wave scattering depends both on the properties of the scatterer and on the geometry of the incoming seismic wavefield. The results show that scattering is strongest when the alignment of geological structures is approximately perpendicular to the direction of wave propagation.

For the 27 July 2014 event, the scattered Love waves have a dominant period of about 10 s and propagate with an apparent

velocity near 3.1 km s^{-1} , significantly slower than the SH waves, which travel at approximately 8.8 km s^{-1} . In the next step, the distance of the scatterer from the seismic station along the path of each beam was calculated separately, and a point was determined for each. For each beam path, the maximum ratio of the scattered wave amplitude to the shear wave amplitude was also calculated, and this value was attributed to the scatterer location on that path. Thus, a map of the domains was drawn for each event. The characteristics of this earthquake, including magnitude, back azimuth, and epicentral distance, are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: The characteristics of the event on 27 July 2014, including magnitude, back azimuth, and epicentral distance. The red triangle is used to indicate seismic stations, and the yellow star indicates the earthquake.

Lastly, the source of the dispersed phases is estimated by backprojecting the envelope of stacked traces (normalized by the SH wave amplitude). Figure 4 shows the geographical location of the scattering points and the general location of the scatterers. The density of points in an area indicates that at that point, the scatterers

acted more strongly and created a Love wave with a larger amplitude. Back-projection mapping reveals a concentration of scattering points in western Turkey. The highest density of scatterers is observed along the Izmir–Ankara–Erzincan tectonic belt, suggesting that this structure strongly influences seismic wave propagation.

Fig. 4: The distribution location obtained in this study, which is located in western Turkey, is marked with a yellow square. The solid black circles with a yellow line are the scatter points, and the green triangles are the seismic stations.

DISCUSSION

Locating seismic scattering sources provides important constraints on tectonic structures, crustal deformation patterns, and the relationship between wave propagation and geological features. Previous studies have shown that body-to-surface wave scattering is typically associated with strong lateral heterogeneities such as topographic gradients, basin edges, fault zones, and Moho offsets [3,13]. The results of this study indicate that the Izmir–Ankara–Erzincan suture zone acts as a significant seismic scatterer. In the slowness-time diagram, 2 different love waves are observed. We consider SH and PS as shear waves to find scatterer points. Since the points obtained from the location of both phases had good overlap, the set of

obtained points was introduced as the distribution locations.

As can be seen in Figure 5, the scatter points obtained in the recent study correspond to the Izmir–Ankara suture zone. As can be seen in Figure the presence of a sharp curvature in the suture zone and small thrust faults caused this area to act as a strong scatterer. Suture zones commonly juxtapose lithological units with contrasting seismic velocities and densities. These contrasts generate impedance discontinuities that enhance the scattering of seismic energy.

Additionally, structural complexities within the region, including fault systems and curved tectonic boundaries, likely contribute to the strong scattering observed in the data.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: (a) The tectonic structure of the Anatolian peninsula and its environs. IAES. Suture zone between Erzincan, Ankara, and Izmir [2]. The distribution location obtained in this study is marked with a yellow square. (b) (A) A simplified map of Turkey's main suture zones and the surrounding area (adapted from Kocyi.it et al. 1995). (B) a simplified map depicting the main compressional features that define the Ankara portion of the AESZ, including the AFFZ-Ankara forced fold zone and the AF-TFZ-Ankara foreland fold-imbricate thrust fault zone; (C) a highly simplified map that roughly depicts the Karakaya orogenic belt[4].

CONCLUSION

Using teleseismic observations from a dense seismic array, we identified strong body-to-surface wave scattering associated with a major tectonic boundary in western Turkey. Phase coherence analysis revealed coherent scattered Love waves with a dominant period of approximately 10 s and a velocity near 3.17 km s^{-1} . Back-projection of the scattered energy indicates that the main scattering sources are located along the Izmir–Ankara–Erzincan suture zone.

These results highlight the effectiveness of body-to-surface wave scattering analysis for imaging strong lateral heterogeneities in the Earth's crust. Major tectonic boundaries such as suture zones and fault systems can act as efficient seismic scatterers and provide valuable insights into lithospheric structure and tectonic evolution.

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